

Logic tafalittle enterprise you pay chinakarms and methodologyof theatreni leaen fan areaac cfatida.

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Annotatsiya: Logic tafalittle enterprise you pay chinakarms and methodologyof theatreni o'rganuvchi fan areaac cfatida was conducted advanced philosophical thoughts ijtimoiysiyosiy information given.

Key words: though the law, outlook, tasavvuf, falsafiy, socio-political thoughts, jadid, the culture, the enlightenment, of the paradoxes category

Access

Principles of logic and evidence for your conclusions out of her bri o'rga known as philosophical research. Fthe items will survey the logic of the system is given as an abstrakt, the abuse can be given items ta'kid or argument. Into the logic of the paradox itself is the problem, the error between takes on the questions of the causes and consequences for garden use. Logic — the science of the basic laws and the form on running though. A history of the development of logic and feel of your form. Initial thoughts on logic. The countries of the east, especially in india, camel into being in china. In ancient times, the structure in philosophy and logic, the form was not an independent science. Originally green in the logic of the philosophy parmenid issues of "Nature" in the moment the game, let's see the eliminate zenon aporiyalarida, it was considered at this level Geraklit or in doctrine. Demokrit of the doctrine in aristotle's doctrine of logic that make sense to a plateau dialektik Sokrashnchnt induktiv metho and highlights. The format of a separate science of the science as the logic of aristotle is associated with the name. The range of issues clarified logic should learn it first. Her "Categories", "interpretation", "analytics first", "Second analytics", "raddiya about

Sofistik", "topik" dedicated to the game of logic is called. Aristotle's logic of "unknown knowledge from knowledge to determine cert", "error thoughts and separated from the idea of the heart-tuvchi" as science describes. Logic after aristotle, basically, stoiklar school representatives , Epikur, loc skeptiklar in the development of the doctrine. Stoiklar logic and truth from the mistakes of the human mind knew that to achieve the purpose of preservation. Of the countries in the middle east was also a form of science of the lateral logic. Also as a developer, an independent scientific philosophy and logic in central asia. The thu, Farobi, ibn test, Amudarya, Umar Novella, alisher navoi, of great thinkers like bedil the service is great. Farobi feel "Logic "introduction, "science of the origin and classification of the" game logic and the scientific metho to know that look in to the issues. Farobi opinion, to know the various mistakes in the process and save lost human logic. Farobi understanding, and their types in the judgment, concluded, and feel sillogizm figura of moduslarini analysis. Sillogizm metho prove the most accurate, the truth is that bri is a metho to do. Ibn sina's "book ashshifo", "annajot Book", "Donishnoma" thoughts on the logic outlined in the works. "agi to handle logic (knowledge), which indicates how to handle detected using agi, the truth, and what is the types of knowledge and how they liest haqiqatsifat and the science has determined that" ibn test was. ¹

Farobi related to the logic of the doctrine of aristotle, ibn test, ibn rushd camel to europe through the works related to logic. The problem with the logic in medieval europe, the main lovely, was studied within the framework of the relations of general and individual concepts. A new era in Dekart r. f. bac upon, t. avicenna's logic, modal logic temporal logic of science v. were negotiated in various area and the other to create. 18 — 19th century, i. kant and the philosophical thoughts in the logic of the system has been created in the name of v. f. rolan play an important. The opinion in the name of philosophical logic available in the form consists of thinking of the object of its study.

¹ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mantiq>

The main objective is to determine the logic of the truth, study the ways to achieve it. Though the Logic of the idea to be the manifestation of the form of connection between the rule of law, including the development and interaction, which indicates the summary of learning. The logic of the consolation — that's the whole idea much remuneration determine the truth. The object of the science of logic is the study of the thoughts of 3 different though in the form of understanding, judgment (review) and will be concluded in the form available. Maintaining access to spark discussion and also as a result of their interaction with other logic that those aris clonal structure (mas, problem, hypothesis, theo the idea, and others)and is realized. Proceedings of the term in the discussion of the achievement of the minimum required to achieve reliable and meet the number on the construction of the idea of the formal aspects include the result be true. The accord, which represents the idea comes to the subject himself, who — called much is the whole idea's remuneration (see the proof). The idea is to build on the requirements can be achieved with the laws of the comp lovely though. Though the laws (see Ayniyat law, Conflict of law, sufficient law, third law of exclude) mu-in the process of doing hokama thoughts (thinking element) consists of communications between the available necessary. Though it is a multifaceted process, various dog on the other hand, in particular, the content and form (structure) or to learn the origins and development can take. This function organizes all of the logic of science, the metho its various (see induktiv in deduktiv in a different direction after each separation, the use in the design of causes.

Logic (from the green. the logos – the so called'z, thoughts, speech, mind) and though the laws of the science of the form. Logic (logika), one of the most ancient science toe"become its is found, the green philosopher aristotle is. "The language of the logos green terma "though", so "z" "aql", "speech", "qonuniyatlike" ma'represents no. "Logic" is equivalent to the term logika the term. Logic is the science of one of the ancient science toe'become centuries, g for"learning in the education system of the toe of the east and across arb necessary'science is at presentone of ards toe'become № tea

in the form of the toe munching the topic'citizens of hours allocated to the French audience, which is total downloads lessonof ulot (in hours) total independent work Ma"ruza Seminar 1-module 1. The basic law of the subject of the science of logic. 2 2 2 4 4 8 of the form as though understanding. Judgment. 8 4 2 2 3 4 concluded. Argumentlash 2 2 4 4 5 8 the logic of the development in the form of knowledge, and comes. The science of logic o"rga get a man toknow a knowledge of abuse univer ko'to payib around inthe moment to communicate with people from the'settings for the organization server. Logic of philosophical knowledge, including the knowledge of science in general all the time, all o'rga is carrying also a necessary condition. Ab mantiqshunos our opinion dalillab great scientistshe Nasr farobi the philosophy of "o'b rga before whatyou should ilish 'fromrising," we will pamphlets referat. Farobi this game, your efforts, writes: "the study of philosophy from earlier error and edashishdan the store, either the wire at the truth'lini tushunto take ib beginner speaker (so'zlovchi) desire of cleaning is necessary. This prove 'fromthe rising science of logic), bilan methodology engage as a result ofhe is ab handle to enter.²

The feelings of Victories univer highway,the movement of things and events i o'a worthy aris is on the basi of the typical domestic law. Binikosi of the man of action in mind, that the thought process is also o'a worthy qonuniyat on the basi of the specific objective is realized. Things and events important in the concept of philosophy of law, it is necessary, in general, represents a stable relationship relative. Mantiqda the law of nature while the Formalelements of the thinking behind hun o'rtasi inner, essential, necessary, the relevant interaction represents. Just the though of the laws of formal logic applies only recently uncovered. The laws of formal logic (or the laws of though) deyilganda fikrlashga meet the minimum required important characteristic of the garden to thegreenhouses due to be understood. Though the laws of the objective reality of the human brain in the form of embodied and reflected for a long time as a result.

²<https://prezi.com/p/jtz5ckacxqqt/mantiq-tafakkur-shakllari-va-qonunlarini-organuvchi-fan-sohasi-sifatida/>

The laws of this thinking from the 'settings fulfillment ta'is minlash. Though they form the toe'of the present concepts, judgments and conclusions , and out of the format of o'represents zaro communications. Qar laws of the superficial thoughas subjective toe agan of law'even I have become, in essence, the objective is to handle the content of ab. Think of all the people th of this law, the universal law, which applies are the same. I have to break the exchange'sbrowsing, o'zgarib you can't update. Taftpay to follow the laws of kk from the 'settings understandable, clear, consistent, without conflict, - based meditation allows. Accuracy, trackoff, free from conflict toe'lish and not proof (the basi) from the 'settings tafakkurlashning are not the main sign. Formal m'antique've ayniyat of the basic law, conflict, third exception, the law of basi are enough.

Ayniyat of law. This law of ko"ra within the framework of a discussion of when the use of an understanding of each terminology, a ma"noda, ya"o"z 8 ma"in nosi must be use. Having in mind the same size toe"lsa, said the thoughts of the aspect from the size of o"that rema after zgarib if the idea is exactly the one. I think about the items or events specific to any given th toe"present all the important characters, the side cover. Despite the constant thinking about the case and how many times to repeat the subject, o"zgarib and the"content iy toe"ladi. The first toe of the property constitute the essence of law, to contemplate this present ayniyat accuracy. Ayniyat law "A – a" (a=a) is based on the formula. For example, the "philosophical laws" and "nature, society, and the most general laws of human though the birth of the concept of" equal to each other, that is. O thoughts of you"ma z"nosi work, and it leads to confusing thoughts ayniyat is a violation of law. For example, someone spoke to the people yolg steam cheat"on. Akhmedov aldama so true without someones spoke, he yolg"oncha not. This conclusion was in error. Ayniyat here because the law is being broker. The first yolg in general"to the people who are speaking on the"g"if it's going rising, the second the moment yolg the same on the basi"to people who did not speaking on"g"rising it's going. Ayniyat simvolik - in-law of the science of logic, ya"to get the judgment manti"and I get the manti predikat"ida o"zi- specific ko"is characterized rinib: for example: from the

philosophical point of view "quality" tushunchas o"worthy toe with specific content'lsa trade this concept by any other content (good, useful) methodology'is llab. Debate-thatearth isin the process of how zara toe'ayniyat intentionally cheat and also the opponent in order to win, the lsa out of the demands of the law, it was an example of the uvchi sofistlar the unit is not'the bodi while limot are called.³

Unviersity of conflict. Two opposite views of the same thing, or phenomenon has been expressed about the same timein the same proportions at the right toe ing'la can't. Of the conflict of law "is also a b, b is also not toe'can't la" is characterized by the formula: Ithough up upon ns clear, obvious toe'libgina rema did not may be, but without conflict toe"lish is also necessary. Conflictspecific to the human though sizlik toe'is one of the most important qualities present. Ma"lum at the same time as the events in the object and objective reality, any featured in the same conditionsalso to handle ab toe"lish, too toe'at lmasmay not be. Time o'the subject of two contrary properties taala zidathe toe of luke'in the form of the conflict of law even though the lmas as the year of the resto. Conflict and contrary to the law of economic relations in the judgment of the opposite methodology"is llab. Thu, the ea when the opposite of judgment , both at the same time the toe error'can lish; o"zaro contrary, the judgment is not an error, while at the same time, the toe of the one I error'lsa, the latter is of course true toe"ladi. The opposite judgmentin m toe while , when su"lmas was ya'from the error that comes out to one of the two I do not chinligi. For example: "Aristotle – found the linear logic of science" and "Aristotle – the way of the logic of science is not found" - this is o"zaro judgment are contrary to. This is contrary to the judgment of the toe, both at the same time error'lmasydi. One is true and the other toe'at ucl present thehun, the latter is the error. O'the toe zaro opposite"present "this sweet drug" and "this bitter drug" of the judgment, while at the same time, the error is the same ratio in both toe"can lish. The drug because of too sweet, too bitter toe"lmas, but bemaza or sour can be. Ba'zida two

³ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mantiqiy_qonunlar

opposite opinions in a conflict in logic toe when I say' can be of lmas. This chair made a statement on the opinions opposite various the timeand said in a different ratio toe'ladi. For example: "subject of the ex 10 on taste not deliver a student at the shops. logic" and "logic. students on the subject when you handed your ex". This judgment contrary to thisdifferent time thai r is true, ya"to the conflict between the I toe'was lmas. Therefore, in the process of thinking, time, relations, and conditions necessary for the preservation of an object, a unit of the validity of law is the conflict.

Summary:

When you conclude, the field of cognitive science of the form and logic of the law though, the study of the conditions is very important. In this field study, research and practice through theories of logic, laws, and are taught the basic principles of logic though. This will help you to understand the structure of the system and its laws subject area to learn the basic principles of management.

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